

Overall Strategy for SSHOC Data Management

Dissemination Level	PU
Date	23 Feb 2022
Work Package	WP 1- Project Management and Administration
Task	T1.1 Administrative Project Management
Type	ORDP: Open Research Data Pilot
Approval Status	N/A
Version	V1.0
Number of Pages	p.1 – p.26

Abstract:

This *Overall strategy for SSHOC data management* offers an update of the original SSHOC Data Management Plan based on a structured, standardised description of data collected, created and used for and by the SSHOC project updated with all current information from SSHOC WP and task leaders.

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History

Version	Date	Reason	Revised by
0.1	15/01/2022	Finalised collection of data and input	Anne Sofie Fink
1.0	23/02/2022	Final version	Anne Sofie Fink

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Executive Summary

This *Overall strategy for SSHOC data management* offers an update of the original SSHOC DMP¹ based on a structured, standardised description of data collected, created and used for and by the SSHOC project updated with all current information from SSHOC WP and task leaders.

The Overall strategy for SSHOC data management accommodates the need for a continuously updated SSHOC DMP for the project period and beyond in line with suggestions for and comments to the SSHOC DMP from the EU reviewer June 2020.

The Overall strategy for SSHOC Data Management consists of:

- Deliverable 1,6: Data Management Plan - DMP
- The report: 'Overall strategy for SSHOC Data Management'
- The appendix: List all data sets

The report 'Overall Strategy for SSHOC Data Management' will act as data management guidelines, best practices and ambitions for data management across the project for the large stages of the SSHOC project and beyond.

In order to comply with the ambition for SSHOC data management to provide a continuous update of the SSHOC DMP the 'List of all data sets' will remain a living document. In this way all WP and task leaders will be encouraged to update the sheet 'List of all data sets' whenever relevant until the end of the SSHOC project.

By the end of the project the sheet will give up-to-date information on data management for all SSHOC resources to support findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability as well as preservation and sustainability.

The 'Overall strategy for SSHOC data management' accommodates the need for a continuously updated SSHOC DMP for the project period and beyond in line with suggestions for and comments to the SSHOC DMP from the EU reviewer June 2020.

The Overall strategy for SSHOC Data Management consists of:

- Deliverable 1,6: Data Management Plan - DMP
- Overall strategy for SSHOC Data Management
- List all data sets and data usage

The 'Overall Strategy for SSHOC Data Management' is based on the following DM supporting initiatives throughout the SSHOC project period:

¹ Ivana Ilijasic Versic, Vanja Komljenovic, Martina Drascic, Irena Vipavc Brvar, Elizabeth Lea Bishop, Daan Broeder, Maria Eskevich, Dieter Van Uytvanck, Maria Gavriilidou, Emiliano Degl'Innocenti, Monica Monachini, Nicolas Larrousse, Wolfgang Schmidle, Laure Barbot, Erzsébet Toth-Czifra, Klaus Illmayer, Matej Ďurčo, Stefan Buddenbohm, Nanette Rissler Pipka, ... Kea Tijdens. (2020). **D1.6 SSHOC Data Management Plan**. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3931491>

- List of all SSHOC datasets and data usage up-to-date
 - Survey data
 - Case studies/pilots data
 - Tools and services data
 - SSHOC Marketplace
 - SSHOC user communities data
 - Other data

- FAIR Overview for all data sets
 - Collection of up-to-date information concerning findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability for metadata, data and data usage
 - To a large extent compliance with the FAR principles across SSHOC
 - Continued push for further development of the FAIRness for SSHOC datasets and data usage throughout the project and ideally beyond

- Solution for sustainability and long-term preservation for all SSHOC metadata and data
 - Check for responsible handling of sustainability and preservation
 - Use of the SSHOC Marketplace for sustainability for access to metadata and data
 - Recommendations for long-term preservation by certified repository (if not already in place)

- Keep the SSHOC DMP alive
 - Open and living document for up-to-date information on data management by the 'List of all datasets and data usage'
 - Links to all SSHOC deliverables and publications to support data management quality in general and sustainability and preservation dimensions specifically.

In conclusion, the Overall Strategy for SSHOC Data Management outlines how data management planning has supported work in the SSHOC project and offers transparency to the SSHOC project's compliance with the FAIR principles as well as how the project supports preservation and sustainability of data sets and data usages during and after the SSHOC project.

Abbreviations and Acronyms²

API	Application Programming Interface
AUSSDA	The Austrian Social Science Data Archive
CAT	Computer-Aided Translation
CAWI	Computer-assisted web interviewing
CDI	Customer data integration
CIDOC-CRM	Comité International pour la Documentation – Conceptual Reference Model
CTS	Core Trust Seal
DANS	Data Archiving and Network Services
DBSS	Dried Blood Spot Samples
DDI	Data Documentation Initiative
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DPO	Data protection officer
EMMs	Ethnic and Migrant minorities
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
E-RIHS	European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science
ESS	European Social Survey
ETHMIGSURVE YDATA	The International Ethnic and Immigrant Minorities' Survey Data Network
EU	European Union
EURHISFIRM	Historical high-quality company-level data for Europe
EVS	European Values Study
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GESIS	Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences
GGP	Generations and Gender Programme
GUI	Graphical User Interface

² The table is shared with the SSHOC DMP:

Ivana Ilijasic Versic, Vanja Komljenovic, Martina Drascic, Irena Vipavc Brvar, Elizabeth Lea Bishop, Daan Broeder, Maria Eskevich, Dieter Van Uytvanck, Maria Gavriilidou, Emiliano Degl'Innocenti, Monica Monachini, Nicolas Larrousse, Wolfgang Schmidle, Laure Barbot, Erzsébet Toth-Czifra, Klaus Illmayer, Matej Ďurčo, Stefan Buddenbohm, Nanette Rissler Pipka, ... Kea Tijdens. (2020). **D1.6 SSHOC Data Management Plan**. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3931491>

HQ	Head Quarters
IIF	International Image Interoperability Framework
IPERION HS	Integrated Platform for the European Research Infrastructure
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
ISCO	International Standard Classification of Occupations
KNAW	Royal Dutch Academy of Science
LIBER	Ligue des Bibliothèques Européennes de Recherche
LOD	Linked Open Data
MCSQ	Multilingual Corpus of Survey Questionnaires
MT	Machine Translation
NIDI	The Netherlands Interdisciplinary Demographic Institute
NLP	Natural language processing
NSD	Norwegian Center for Research Data
OEAW	Austrian Academy of Sciences
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OLA	Operation Level Agreement
PID	Persistent identifiers
PDF	Portable Document Format
RI	Research infrastructure
SAS	Statistical Analysis Software
SHARE	Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SPSS	Statistical Package for the Social Sciences
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
TEI	Text Encoding Initiative
TGIR	Très grande infrastructure de recherche
TMX	Translation Memory Exchange
SSHOC	Social Science and Humanities Open Cloud
UK	United Kingdom
UPF	Pompeu Fabra University
XML	Extensible Markup Language
WP	Work Package

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1. Introduction

SSHOC - "Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud" project (GA No.823782) is one of the 5 ongoing EOSC thematic cluster projects. SSHOC aims to provide a full-fledged Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud where data, tools, and training are available and accessible for users of SSH data. It will build the SSH Cloud, maximise the re-use through Open Science and FAIR principles, interconnect existing and new infrastructures, and establish governance for SSH-EOSC. Development, realisation and maintenance of user-friendly tools & services will allow aligning, analysing, presenting and encompassing vast heterogeneous collections of SSH data available within data repositories and other institutions in Europe.

SSHOC project objectives and activities are set to enable data collecting, processing, usage, re-usage and accession in line with high standards and generally acknowledged data management regulations and procedures. Project participates in the Pilot on Open Research Data in Horizon 2020, in line with the Commission's Open Access to research data policy for facilitating access, reuse and preservation of its research data. It is also aligned with the European Commission's approach towards research data which is "as open as possible, as closed as needed" and with provisions of the GA.

This *Overall strategy for SSHOC data management* offers an update of the original SSHOC DMP³ based on a structured, standardised description of data collected, created and used for and by the SSHOC project updated with all current information from SSHOC WP and task leaders.

The SSHOC project consortium has the expertise to cover the whole data cycle: from data creation and curation to optimal re-use of data, as well as addressing training and advocacy to increase actual re-use of data.

*"The **Data Management Plan (DMP)** is one of the main SSHOC project management documents. It gives an overview of data handling during and after the SSHOC project implementation and provides information on creation, management, sharing, curation and preservation of the project data and data usage for implementation of project activities."* (D1.6 SSHOC Data Management Plan_30.06.2020._v1.0 final Word)

The Overall strategy for SSHOC data management accommodates the need for a continuously updated SSHOC DMP for the project period and beyond in line with suggestions for and comments to the SSHOC DMP from the EU reviewer June 2020.

³ Ivana Ilijasic Versic, Vanja Komljenovic, Martina Drascic, Irena Vipavc Brvar, Elizabeth Lea Bishop, Daan Broeder, Maria Eskevich, Dieter Van Uytvanck, Maria Gavriilidou, Emiliano Degl'Innocenti, Monica Monachini, Nicolas Larrousse, Wolfgang Schmidle, Laure Barbot, Erzsébet Toth-Czifra, Klaus Illmayer, Matej Ďurčo, Stefan Buddenbohm, Nanette Rissler Pipka, ... Kea Tijdens. (2020). **D1.6 SSHOC Data Management Plan**. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3931491>

The Overall strategy for SSHOC Data Management consists of:

- Deliverable 1,6: Data Management Plan - DMP
- Overall strategy for SSHOC Data Management
- List all data sets

The report will act as data management guidelines, best practices and ambitions for data management across the project for the large stages of the SSHOC project and beyond. In order to comply with the ambition for SSHOC data management to provide a continuous update of the SSHOC DMP the 'List of all data sets' will remain a living document. In this way all WP and task leaders will be encouraged to update the sheet whenever relevant. By the end of the project the sheet will give up-to-date information on data management for all SSHOC resources to support findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability as well as preservation and sustainability.

1.1 Approach to the SSHOC DMP update

In the Spring of 2021 the WP1 initiated an internal report delivering a plan for how to update the SSHOC DMP in line with the suggestions from the EC Review⁴.

Listed here are the action points supporting an integrated and overall approach towards data management in SSHOC:

- **From DMP with data specificity to overview of SSHOC data**
Action point 1: List of all datasets in one scheme
- **From specific descriptions for each data set to overall SSHOC data's FAIR accommodation**
Action point 2: FAIR Overview for all data sets
- **Focus on sustainability and long-term preservation of all SSHOC metadata and data**
Action point 3: Provide solution for sustainability and preservation more explicitly
- **Keeping the SSHOC DMP alive**
Action point 4: Make a plan to update the SSHOC DMP
- **Ethics and GDPR – from data set unique to shared approach**
Action point 5: Shared approach towards ethics and GDPR in SSHOC
- **Only data and metadata are covered by the DMP**
Action point 6: SSHOC DMP scope is data and metadata (as-is)

The DMP update is an independent document additional to the original SSHOC DMP, already approved by the EC. In this way the updated DMP is not a substitute for the original DMP but an addition to this document. The SSHOC DMP Update is published and available in Zenodo.

In conclusion, the SSHOC DMP Update points to how data management planning has supported the SSHOC project incl. complies with the FAIR principles as well as supports preservation and sustainability of data sets and data usages during and after the SSHOC project.

⁴ Internal CESSDA review for SSHOC Deliverable 1.6: Data Management Plan - DMP

The approach to the update of the SSHOC DMP will accommodate comments from the EU Review as well as the shift the focus from data management in process to sustainable data management in an **Overall strategy for SSHOC Data Management**.

All detailed updated information on data management for datasets and data usage is provided by the responsible WP leaders and task leaders.

The original SSHOC Data Management Plan

The SSHOC DMP covers an ambitious and challenging variety of data sets from classic survey data sets on attitudes and behaviour over physical measurements to data dissemination via SSHOC Marketplace. The datasets and data use originate from a broad range of research objectives and thereby present the great span of the research fields of the social sciences and humanities. Additionally, the SSHOC DMP is viewed as a living document supporting the SSHOC datasets and data usage throughout the project period and beyond. The WP1 team started working on the follow-up and addressing the EC Reviewer's comments early in 2021 to make sure that all comments are taken into account.

The original SSHOC DMP was structured by datasets and data usages individually: Survey data, case studies/pilots data, tools and services data, SSHOC Marketplace, SSHOC user communities data, and other data rather than by work packages. The value of the SSHOC DMP was positively acknowledged by the EU reviewer. However, the reviewer recommended getting an overall strategy about data management ensuring sustainability of the data, version control, etc. added to the original DMP. Additionally, it was suggested to show the commonality and a common underlying approach towards data management in SSHOC and assemble all aspects of data management from other Work Packages in the Data Management Plan.

Accommodation of the EU Review of the SSHOC DMP

The value of the SSHOC DMP was positively acknowledged by the EU reviewer.

Comment from EU review to the original SSHOC DMP:

"The DMP outlines the different types of data and the different policies that will be respected for each category of data according to the European policies. Ethical and gender issues have also been accounted for. However, it would be recommendable if the data management plan also contains an overall strategy about data management ensuring sustainability of the data, version control, etc. in order to show the commonality and a common underlying approach towards data management. Other deliverables contain aspects of data management that can be assembled in the Data Management Plan." (SSHOC Review Report)

The update of the DMP is based on an internal review carried out in order to pick up on the EU reviewer's point of moving forward towards an overall strategy, sustainability for data as well as commonality and common underlying approach for SSHOC.

The Overall Strategy for SSHOC Data Management

The review comments and suggestions for follow-up action points are additional and optional to the General project review. The action points add value to the SSHOC DMP and especially support the DMP transparency for accommodating the FAIR principles and thereby future usage of the SSHOC data sets.

The SSHOC project and obviously the DMP covers an ambitious and challenging variety of data sets from classic survey data sets on attitudes over physical measurements to GIS coordinates on migration routes. The datasets originate from a broad range of research objectives and thereby presents the research fields of the social sciences and humanities very well.

Below is listed review comments and suggestions for action points supporting a more integrated and overall approach towards up-dated data management in SSHOC.

Review comments and action points in summary:

- **From DMP with data specificity to overview of SSHOC data**
Action point 1: List of all datasets and data usage in one scheme
- **From specific descriptions for each data set to overall SSHOC data's FAIR accommodation**
Action point 2: FAIR Overview for all data sets
- **Focus on sustainability and long-term preservation of all SSHOC metadata and data**
Action point 3: Provide solution for sustainability and preservation more explicitly
- **Keeping the SSHOC DMP alive**
Action point 4: Make a plan to update the SSHOC DMP
- **Ethics and GDPR – from data set unique to shared approach**
Action point 5: Shared approach towards ethics and GDPR in SSHOC
- **Only data and metadata are covered by the DMP – let us keep it there!**
Action point 6: SSHOC DMP scope is data and metadata (as-is)

The Overall Strategy for SSHOC Data Management at hand is structured according to these action points with the exception of the *action points 5: Shared approach towards ethics and GDPR in SSHOC* and *action point 6: 'Only data and metadata are covered by the DMP – let us keep it there!'*

It is decided to leave out the intention of a shared approach towards ethics and GDPR in SSHOC due to the fact that SSHOC primarily is based on already existing data resources with very well-established procedures for handling GDPR and additional data security concerns. All procedures are presented in extensive detail in the original SSHOC DMP.

A majority of the deliverables for SSHOC are concerned with metadata and data usage where issues on GDPR and data security are of less or no interest. Although, a lot of the SSHOC data are covered by GDPR which will have varied interpretations in different countries. Therefore looking across datasets of different national origins will be less relevant.

In line with the common understanding of the FAIR principles the whole range of digital objects/research products could be addressed by a data management plan – e.g. Computer Assisted Translation Tools are a digital object and could be addressed in a DMP in line with the FAIR principles.

The original SSHOC DMP focused on data and metadata in the project. It is the decision that the ‘Overall Strategy for SSHOC Data Management’ is focused on the data sets and data usage in SSHOC as outlined in the SSHOC DMP. In this way e.g. software has been defined outside the scope of this strategy in order to focus and succeed within the originally defined scope.

2. Overall Strategy for SSHOC Data Management

The ‘Overall strategy for SSHOC data management’ accommodates the need for a continuously updated SSHOC DMP for the project period and beyond in line with suggestions for and comments to the SSHOC DMP from the EU reviewer June 2020.

The Overall strategy for SSHOC Data Management consists of:

- Deliverable 1.6: Data Management Plan - DMP
- The report: ‘Overall strategy for SSHOC Data Management’
- The appendix: List all data sets (v1.0 in time of publication of this report)

The ‘Overall Strategy for SSHOC Data Management’ is based on the following DM supporting initiatives throughout the SSHOC project period:

- List of all SSHOC datasets and data usage
- FAIR Overview for all data sets
- Solution for sustainability and long-term preservation for all SSHOC metadata and data
- Keep the SSHOC DMP alive

The Overall Strategy for SSHOC Data Management outlines how data management planning will support work in the SSHOC project and offers transparency to the SSHOC project’s compliance with the FAIR principles as well as how the project supports preservation and sustainability of data sets and data usages during and after the SSHOC project.

2.1 List of all SSHOC data sets and data usage up-to-date

The original SSHOC DMP⁵ provided a structured description of data collected, created and used for and by the SSHOC project incl. tools and services as well as a SSHOC marketplace. That is unlike the SSHOC project description, the structure for SSHOC Data Management Plan is according to data collections and usages in SSHOC rather than the SSHOC work packages:

- Survey data
- Case studies/pilots data
- Tools and services data
- SSHOC Marketplace
- SSHOC user communities data
- Other data

The SSHOC project consortium has the expertise to cover the whole data cycle: from data creation and curation to optimal re-use of data, as well as addressing training and advocacy to increase actual re-use of data.

The DMP activities for each data set or data usage focused on the specific data set in question. With the ‘Overall Strategy for SSHOC data management’ the intention is to shift perspective from data specificity in the original DMP to overview of SSHOC data sets and usage. However, the strategy must cover a portfolio of many individual DMP’s aimed at the individual data sets and usage. Therefore it is necessary for SSHOC to have the overall strategy supported by detailed descriptions for the specific data sets and usage for the formulation of the strategy:

Action point 1: List of all datasets and data usage in one scheme

Based on the list it will be possible to point the commonalities and shared approaches towards data management planning and compliance with the FAIR principles within the SSHOC project. When relevant for a data collection or usage resource, a link for access is added in the list.

The table below presents SSHOC data collections and usages in the original DMP linked to the SSHOC work packages which are responsible for delivery of resources for actual and future research.

⁵ Ivana Ilijasic Versic, Vanja Komljenovic, Martina Drascic, Irena Vipavc Brvar, Elizabeth Lea Bishop, Daan Broeder, Maria Eskevich, Dieter Van Uytvanck, Maria Gavriilidou, Emiliano Degl’Innocenti, Monica Monachini, Nicolas Larrousse, Wolfgang Schmidle, Laure Barbot, Erzsébet Toth-Czifra, Klaus Illmayer, Matej Ďurčo, Stefan Buddenbohm, Nanette Rissler Pipka, ... Kea Tijdens. (2020). **D1.6 SSHOC Data Management Plan**. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3931491>

Table 1: Presentation of SSHOC data sets' and data usages' as actual and future SSH resources

<p>Survey data</p>	<p>Several cross-national surveys have been part of the SSHOC consortia, the biggest ones being SHARE (Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe) and ESS (European Social Survey).</p> <p>Data produced during regular data collections (rounds) is used in the SSHOC project for various purposes (from testing tools, creating pilots/case studies, enhancing mechanisms for data protection, security and access, to designing user services).</p>
<p>Case studies / pilots data</p>	<p>Implementation of the SSHOC project anticipates pilots and case-studies with the purpose of implementing enhancements and upgrades in the existing methodologies and technologies:</p> <p>Task 3.1 Case-study for piloting NLP technologies for translation The collected and enriched multilingual metadata and taxonomies will be useful to maximise the accessibility and to improve discovery by users that are non-native language speakers.</p> <p>Task 3.3 Case-studies for piloting NLP technologies for text analysis The case study foresees two axes for data collection: domain and language. Focused Twitter collections will be created using specific keywords, depending on the domain (e.g. xenophobia or covid19) and the languages (Greek or English), with the support of dedicated NLP technologies.</p> <p>Task 4.1 A sample management system for cross-national web surveys The case develops a data management system for cross-national web surveys based on data from ESS Round 10 pilot.</p> <p>Task 4.4 Applying Computer Assisted Translation tools in Social Surveys A pilot study on the use machine translation (MT) in questionnaire translation using already existing survey questions from ESS and European Values Study (EVS). The case will generate translation-related data, for instance, review (final) and interim translation versions, machine translation output and post-edited version and background information on the translators (participants) to the pilot study.</p> <p>Task 4.4 Voice recorded interviews and audio analysis Summary statistics of the audio data, as described in the work description, will be made available alongside the standard GGP survey data file.</p> <p>Task 4.5 Social policy APIs for social surveys The data is not sensitive and integrates the algorithm inherent in existing, publicly available social policy datasets such as the OECD family policy calculator into the Generations and Gender Survey workflow.</p> <p>Task 3.7 LOD archaeology case study</p>

	<p>A virtual reconstruction of the Roman theatre in Catania as an example of an actual transition of archaeological data to the cloud. Data will be generated for all stages of the workflow from an archaeological excavation/survey to a 3D reconstruction of the site.</p>
<p>Tools and services data</p>	<p>Task 3.2 Selected Ontologies and Vocabularies A specialised repository for socio-economic surveys for their long-list questions about respondent’s occupation, religion (In progress), education and industry. Vocabulary and data are available for web surveys and CAPI surveys. The data are useful for any multi-country survey asking for long-list questions about respondent’s occupation, religion, education and industry.</p> <p>Task 3.6, 3.4 and 3.5 Making Data Findable by being Citable, task 3.5 Data and Metadata Interoperability Hub and Making Data Re-usable and actionable All service and tool development activities are required to make results available on GitHub under open software license. Production level services and tools will be made to comply with the GDPR regarding managing user credentials and attributes. The data collected will be backed up regularly by the host ACDH-CH/OEAW who operates the installation. The ConversionHub information will also be harvested and preserved in the SSH Open Marketplace (https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/) for accessibility and sustainability.</p> <p>Task 4.2 Preparing tools for the use of Computer Assisted Translation Task team will produce a multilingual corpus of survey questionnaires, namely the Multilingual Corpus of Survey Questionnaires (MCSQ) using already existing survey questions from ESS, EVS and SHARE in a later iteration. Output formats are SQL compatible: TMX, CSV and XML. ESS, EVS and SHARE questionnaires will be re-used. The data are useful to corpus linguists, translation scholars and practitioners, cross-cultural survey methodologists.</p> <p>Task 4.6 Semantic annotation of Heritage Science Data Semantic annotations enriched by multiple users are provided as well as a tool for the description of 3D models for various studies in SSH as a collaborative platform. Users can share their observations on the data in an interdisciplinary approach. The types of data: Digital Asset generate/collect; Photogrammetry Objects; Annotations (user descriptors, text, number, attachments, reports, etc.); Images; Dense 3D point clouds; Geometric descriptors (normal, curvature, ambient occlusions). The formats of data: .ply for Point Cloud; .json for computed description; .csv for user descriptors. The data are useful to: Curators; Restorers; Researchers; Historians; Archaeologists; Architects; Engineers;</p>

	<p>Physicists; and Chemists.</p> <p>Task 5.2 Hosting and sharing data repositories The development of a research data repository service on EOSC, for SSH institutes currently without such a facility for their designated communities.</p> <p>Task 5.6 Issues in providing Open Data in Heritage Science and Archaeology Documentation of the process of re-formatting two existing data sets to demonstrate how they can be presented as examples of FAIR Heritage Science data sets, as a model for future work. The data sets may well be presented in several forms, as a minimum requirement they will be presented via human readable graphical user interfaces, as individually resolvable URIs and as machine actionable structured XML/RDF documents. In addition to the actual datasets some of the modelling processes and examples will also be presented in an interactive and re-usable manner. The data will be useful for any Heritage Scientists, or Art Historian or Conservators, they will also be of use to Digital Humanities. The created FAIR datasets will also be directly re-used to test the development of Heritage Science documentation software as part of the work within the task.</p>
SSHOC Marketplace	<p>The SSH Open Marketplace primary data is metadata. As an aggregator, the Marketplace collects metadata from third party catalogues, which are publicly available sources.</p>
SSHOC user communities data	<p>Ethnic and migration studies A data hub complemented by 2 main components: <i>EMM Survey Registry</i>: A free, online, and user-friendly tool to search for and discover specific surveys using the survey-level metadata, as well as survey-level metadata shared and added to the registry by data producers themselves. <i>EMM Question Data Bank</i> (pilot version): A pilot version of the EMM-dedicated component of the CESSDA-led Euro Question Bank (EQB) to test the feasibility of setting up a full-scale version that allows users to search for specific question items, as well as learn about existing survey questionnaires through the questionnaire and question-level metadata.</p> <p>Task 9.3 Electoral studies An Open Research Knowledge Graph in the field of Electoral Studies. Taxonomies and ontologies underlying the Knowledge Graph with active involvement of the user community. The project will harvest-integrate-interlink-analyse national, European and cross-national data on citizens' electoral behaviour (mainly survey data) and relevant additional data (e.g. contextual data) from existing (open) sources and repositories. The overall results will be integrated in an election studies analytics dashboard to access analytics and visualisations in an easy to use manner, to export results, and to query the data (for more advanced</p>

	<p>users) via a data API for further analysis using common stat packs such as STATA, SPSS or R. The project and some of its services will be provided as part of the SSHOC Marketplace. To maximise the actual use of the outcomes by the user community, and to enhance that the resulting Knowledge Graph will be self-sustaining and continuously updated, the project will be characterised by a demand and user-driven approach.</p> <p>Heritage Science and Humanities datasets</p> <p>Open directories and repositories of digital data will be created hosting information about the available instruments and archives, as well as scientific project results. These will be made available online. There is a strong commitment in the HS community to effectively manage the generated research data. Each of the 52 participating facilities may manage several data sets. In total more than 100 different kinds of data sets are expected within the partnership. Valuable information and metadata generated by the HS community will be reused in various contexts and research scenarios, across disciplines, actions, research and services.</p> <p>“Historical high-quality company-level data for Europe” design study</p> <p>EURHISFIRM “Historical high-quality company-level data for Europe” is a design study to build a world- class research infrastructure (RI) compliant to the FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) data principles. The project aims to increase the accessibility and usability of historical company-level data (financial, governance, and geographical) and to expand the available pool of this data.</p>
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Reference: SSHOC DMP⁶

The original SSHOC Data Management Plan provided a textual presentation of data management planning according to the ‘Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020’⁷ for each of datasets and data usage: Survey data, case studies/pilots data, tools and services data, SSHOC Marketplace, SSHOC user communities data and other data.

For the the ‘Overall Strategy for SSHOC Data Management’ there is produced a structured collection of information for the specific categories/questions in the ‘Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020’ as a ‘List of all datasets and data usage in one scheme’:

- The handling of research data during and after the end of the project

⁶ Ivana Ilijasic Versic, Vanja Komljenovic, Martina Drascic, Irena Vipavc Brvar, Elizabeth Lea Bishop, Daan Broeder, Maria Eskevich, Dieter Van Uytvanck, Maria Gavriilidou, Emiliano Degl'Innocenti, Monica Monachini, Nicolas Larrousse, Wolfgang Schmidle, Laure Barbot, Erzsébet Toth-Czifra, Klaus Illmayer, Matej Ďurčo, Stefan Buddenbohm, Nanette Rissler Pipka, ... Kea Tijdens. (2020). **D1.6 SSHOC Data Management Plan**. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3931491>

⁷ Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020:

https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf

- What data will be collected, processed and/or generated
- Which methodology and standards will be applied
- Whether data will be shared/made open access
- How data will be curated and preserved (including after the end of the project)

The collection of information for this list with update of the SSHOC DMP for the overall strategy compiles information from the original DMP as well as the updates on planned and unplanned developments in the DMP for data collections and - usage.

All WP leaders supported by respective task leaders have added and up-dated information for the list.

The 'List of all datasets and data usage' will be additional to the original The SSHOC Data Management Plan as well as to the 'Overall Strategy'.

In SSHOC the ambition is that data management planning is an ongoing process. Therefore the 'List of all datasets and data usage' will stay as an open live document in order to allow WP - and task leaders continuous update of the information in the list.

For the 'Overall Strategy for SSHOC Data Management' an up-to-date status quo version of the **'List of all datasets and data usage v1.0'** will be published as an appendix to this strategy.

Initially all information in the original DMP was laid out in detail according to specific categories/questions in the Horizon2020 Data Management Plan template, the FAIR Principles and GDPR.

In the detailed list updated information on data preservation and accessibility are put forward among other things. In many cases this information and/or these decisions are made as part of deliverables and as such with the continuous update get linked to the DMP as a living document.

The 'List of all data sets and data usage' offers up-to-date information on data management and in that way insights into overall compliance with the FAIR principles.

2.2 FAIR Overview for all datasets and data usage

The FAIR principles have been received, recognized and complied with across research supporting institutions in Europe and beyond. The FAIR principles are a game changer in the field of research data services for re-use and preservation.

"The FAIR data principles mark an important refinement of the concepts needed to give data greater value and enhance their propensity for reuse, by humans and at scale by machines. For this to be the case, data should be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable to the greatest extent possible. FAIR is a

significant concept in its own right since it offers a set of principles to enhance the usefulness of data.”
(Turning FAIR into Reality⁸)

Often we tend to focus on the communicative aspects of the FAIR principles. However, the FAIR principles were originally primarily developed to support machine-to-machine interaction. The FAIR Principles were developed to facilitate knowledge discovery by assisting humans and machines in their discovery of, access to, integration and analysis of, task-appropriate scientific data and their associated algorithms and workflows.⁹

The original SSHOC DMP provided a description of compliance with the FAIR principles for each data set and data usage specifically. Based on the ‘List of all data sets and data usage’ it is possible to get insights into the overall compliance with the FAIR principles across SSHOC.

Due to the exceptionally large and varied number of data sets and data usage it would be of value to add a structured presentation of the accommodation of the FAIR DM guidelines for each data set and data usage. Obviously, the FAIR Overview must be an interpretation of the ‘List of all data sets and data usage’.

Action point 2: FAIR Overview for all data sets

Based on the overview scheme it is possible to point and document the commonalities and shared approaches towards FAIR and data management planning within SSHOC. Moreover, best practices and suggestions for recommendations for extended FAIR compliance are added.

Potentially missing information or gaps in the accommodation of the FAIR principles for individual data sets will be revealed by producing an overview.

For FAIR compliance across SSHOC, datasets and data usage applies:

- Persistent identifiers
 - DOI - Digital Object Identifier¹⁰
 - ORCID - Open Researcher and Contributor ID¹¹
- The DDI - Data Documentation Initiative - metadata standard¹²: <https://ddialliance.org>
- Open access to data after the principle ‘as open as possible, as closed as necessary’

Best practices for extended FAIR compliance for SSHOC

- Extended support for data re-use as e.g. ESS that offers an online analysis option¹³

⁸ Turning FAIR into Reality: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/turning_fair_into_reality_1.pdf

⁹ The FAIR Principles and guidelines: <https://www.force11.org/group/fairgroup/fairprinciples>

¹⁰ DOI - Digital Object Identifier: <https://www.doi.org/>

¹¹ ORCID - Open Researcher and Contributor ID: <https://orcid.org/>

¹² The DDI - Data Documentation Initiative - metadata standard: <https://ddialliance.org>

¹³ Extended support for data re-use as e.g. ESS that offers an online analysis option:
<http://nesstar.ess.nsd.uib.no/webview/>

Recommendations for extended FAIR compliance for SSHOC

- Standardised access conditions for datasets machine actionable to support interoperability
- Application of public certified data repositories/archives for all SSHOC metadata and data e.g. the certification 'Core Trust Seal'¹⁴

Commonalities and shared approaches towards FAIR and DMP for SSHOC (and beyond)

The initiative FORCE11 gives an elaboration of the FAIR principles into guidelines for operationalisation of the FAIR principles¹⁵, see Table 2.2.

Based on the 'List of all datasets and data usage' that allows a 'FAIR Overview for alle data sets' the table in third columns gives an overall interpretation of compliance with the FAIR principles across SSHOC (FAIR for SSHOC (meta)data).

Table 2: Set of guiding principles to make data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable

The FAIR Principles	Guiding principles for F, A, I and R	FAIR for SSHOC (meta)data
Findability	F1. (meta)data are assigned a globally unique and eternally persistent identifier.	In SSHOC persistent identifiers are assigned to metadata and data with very few exceptions
	F2. data are described with rich metadata.	In SSHOC metadata is of high priority both as project deliverables per se and as description of data e.g. for survey data
	F3. (meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource.	By delivery of the SSHOC Marketplace the SSHOC project offers such a resource. Additionally, SSHOC (meta)data is handled by SSH ERICs.
	F4. metadata specify the data identifier.	
Accessibility	A1 (meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol.	The SSHOC Marketplace applies a standardized communication protocol as does the SSH ERICs.
	A1.1 the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable.	The protocol for SSHOC Marketplace is plemenable the same for the SSH ERICs.
	A1.2 the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary.	In SSHOC most metadata is openly available.

¹⁴ The certification 'Core Trust Seal': <https://www.coretrustseal.org/>

¹⁵ The FAIR principles operationalised: <https://force11.org/info/the-fair-data-principles/>

		In SSHOC often these procedures are carried out by the relevant data repositories.
	A2 metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available.	The SSHOC Marketplace harvests (meta)data so accessibility will be based on the repositories and SSH ERIC, which are to a large extent compliant with the FAIR principles, too.
Interoperability	I1. (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.	In SSHOC many WP's have been concerned with production of translatable metadata resources incl. applying English as additional language
	I2. (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles.	Whenever relevant vocabularies have been developed and published to comply with the FAIR principles.
	I3. (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data.	The SSHOC Marketplace act as a distributed service based on harvesting metadata published on the net.
Reusability	R1. meta(data) have a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes.	Especially the survey data in SSHOC are based on extensive focus on providing elaborate metadata.
	R1.1. (meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage licence.	Licences for SSHOC data are traced back to data publishers and services providers.
	R1.2. (meta)data are associated with their provenance.	For SSHOC (meta)data again extensive standardised metadata are produced incl. Provenance. For SSH data provenance is most often essential for analysis.
	R1.3. (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards.	All SSHOC (meta)data are directly linked to SSH domain and apply relevant standards.

Summing up it is the assessment that across SSHOC the data sets and data usage to a large extent are compliant with the FAIR principles. However, the FAIR principles are *principles* not criteria to be judged to be fulfilled or not. Therefore, this Overall Strategy must push for further development of the FAIRness for SSHOC datasets and data usage towards the end of the project and ideally beyond.

2.3 Solutions for sustainability and preservation

Preservation of data and metadata have not been given a place within the FAIR principles as e.g. pointed out in the report 'Turning FAIR into Reality':

"The FAIR principles focus on access to the data and do not explicitly address the long-term preservation needed to ensure that this access endures. Data should be stored in a trusted and sustainable digital repository to provide reassurances about the standard of stewardship and the commitment to preserve." (Turning FAIR into Reality¹⁶)

A similar point is found in the report 'FAIR Forever? Long Term Data Preservation Roles and Responsibilities, Final Report'¹⁷. Often you may find that accessibility - the A in FAIR - is made to make a substitute for preservation.

Additionally, data and metadata preservation is not part of the vision for the EOSC - European Open Science Cloud. However, absent in FAIR and EOSC, it is acknowledged that preservation as an aspect in data management is a most important aspect for sustainability.

This aspect is described in the CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide:

*"Data management [l]ooks forward to the future, making it clear that you should provide detailed and structured documentation to be able to share your data with other colleagues and prepare them for long-term availability."*¹⁸

The concept of sustainability and preservation is little mentioned in the DMP. Primarily in general terms and only specifically for cultural heritage data.

Action point 3: Provide solution for sustainability and preservation more explicitly

For any project sustainability is an issue of great importance and more and more so as a project comes to an end. To support the SSHOC DMP this 'Overall strategy will go add substance to the original DMP on the subjects of sustainability and preservation of metadata and data and data usage.

In the 'List of all data sets and data usage' (see above, Action point 1) detailed information on sustainability and preservation are collected and presented. By having this information put forward in detail for metadata, data and data usage across SSHOC it is possible to state that sustainability and preservation solutions for SSHOC support future availability of these SSHOC assets.

¹⁶ Turning FAIR into Reality: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/turning_fair_into_reality_1.pdf

¹⁷ FAIR Forever? Long Term Data Preservation Roles and Responsibilities, Final Report: <https://zenodo.org/badge/DOI/10.5281/zenodo.4574234.svg>

¹⁸ Benefits of data management according to the CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide: <https://www.cessda.eu/Training/Training-Resources/Library/Data-Management-Expert-Guide/1.-Plan/Benefits-of-data-management>

The SSHOC Project delivers the SSHOC Marketplace (WP7) as a curated domain specific platform. The SSHOC Marketplace will likely become part of the EOSC and thereby provide sustainable accessibility for metadata and data:

“The Marketplace is mainly a portal intended to be used by humans and machines to find tools, services, datasets and training materials. Thus, discoverability and findability are one of the main goals of the Marketplace. Actually, by building links between metadata collected from various sources and the creation of normalised content supported by community-driven curation, the Marketplace provides a common access to a set of different resources. Every entry from the Marketplace will be assigned an identifier.” (DMP)

Where decisions on/plans for preservation of metadata, data and data usage are missing in the list it is recommended that CESSDA takes on the responsibility for pointing to a certified data archive among the CESSDA Service Providers to provide sustainability, preservation and reuse support.

2.4 Plan to update the SSHOC DMP

In the original SSHOC DMP it is stated:

“The SSHOC Data Management Plan is a living document and shall be updated continuously throughout the project in line with the new information gathered via conducting the project activities.”

However, the DMP does not mention how, when and by whom the plan will be updated:

Action point 4: Make a plan to update the SSHOC DMP

The ‘Overall Strategy for SSHOC Data Management’ accommodates this ambition for ‘keeping the DMP alive’ by offering the ‘List of all datasets and data usage’ as an open document throughout the SSHOC project allowing special attention towards the sustainability and preservation dimensions incl. links to where to find the resources.

WP and task leaders will update the information in the list when relevant until the end of the SSHOC project. By providing up-to-date information on all SSHOC assets in the form of metadata, data and data usage future service providers and data users will be guided to the exact resource (incl. information on version no., licensing, access conditions etc.)

Additionally, it is the intention to add relevant links to all SSHOC deliverables and publications to the list in order to support data management quality in general and sustainability and preservation dimensions specifically before the end of the SSHOC project period.

3. Conclusion

The ‘Overall strategy for SSHOC data management’ accommodates the need for a continuously updated SSHOC DMP for the project period and beyond in line with suggestions for and comments to the SSHOC DMP from the EU reviewer June 2020.

The Overall strategy for SSHOC Data Management consists of:

- Deliverable 1,6: Data Management Plan - DMP
- The report: ‘Overall strategy for SSHOC Data Management’
- List all data sets and data usage

The ‘Overall Strategy for SSHOC Data Management’ is based on the following DM supporting initiatives throughout the SSHOC project period:

- List of all SSHOC datasets and data usage up-to date
 - Survey data
 - Case studies/pilots data
 - Tools and services data
 - SSHOC Marketplace
 - SSHOC user communities data
 - Other data
- FAIR Overview for all data sets
 - Collection of up-to-date information concerning findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability for metadata, data and data usage
 - To a large extent compliance with the FAIR principles across SSHOC
 - Continued push for further development of the FAIRness for SSHOC datasets and data usage throughout the project and ideally beyond
- Solution for sustainability and long-term preservation for all SSHOC metadata and data
 - Check for responsible handling of sustainability and preservation
 - Use of the SSHOC Marketplace for sustainability for access to metadata and data
 - Recommendations for long-term preservation by certified repository (if not already in place)
- Keep the SSHOC DMP alive
 - Open and living document for up-to-date information on data management by the ‘List of all datasets and data usage’
 - Links to all SSHOC deliverables and publications to support data management quality in general and sustainability and preservation dimensions specifically.

In conclusion, the Overall Strategy for SSHOC Data Management outlines how data management planning has supported work in the SSHOC project and offers transparency to the SSHOC project's compliance with the FAIR principles as well as how the project supports preservation and sustainability of data sets and data usages during and after the SSHOC project.

For the case studies/pilots data in the SSHOC DMP the following lines are put forward:

"In the short term, the first data providers are the research infrastructures involved in SSHOC. In the long term, the origin of the data could become any relevant SSH repository in the European research area." (SSHOC DMP¹⁹)

With the 'Overall strategy for SSHOC data management' it is hopefully to be claimed that this is not limited to SSHOC case studies and pilots data but a description of the future potential across all datasets and data usage in SSHOC.

¹⁹ Ivana Ilijasic Versic, Vanja Komljenovic, Martina Drascic, Irena Vipavc Brvar, Elizabeth Lea Bishop, Daan Broeder, Maria Eskevich, Dieter Van Uytvanck, Maria Gavriilidou, Emiliano Degl'Innocenti, Monica Monachini, Nicolas Larrousse, Wolfgang Schmidle, Laure Barbot, Erzsébet Toth-Czifra, Klaus Illmayer, Matej Ďurčo, Stefan Buddenbohm, Nanette Rissler Pipka, ... Kea Tijdens. (2020). **D1.6 SSHOC Data Management Plan**. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3931491>

4. References (in order of appearance)

Ivana Ilijasic Versic, Vanja Komljenovic, Martina Drascic, Irena Vipavc Brvar, Elizabeth Lea Bishop, Daan Broeder, Maria Eskevich, Dieter Van Uytvanck, Maria Gavriilidou, Emiliano Degl'Innocenti, Monica Monachini, Nicolas Larrousse, Wolfgang Schmidle, Laure Barbot, Erzsébet Toth-Czifra, Klaus Illmayer, Matej Ďurčo, Stefan Buddenbohm, Nanette Rissler Pipka, ... Kea Tijdens. (2020). **D1.6 SSHOC Data Management Plan**. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3931491>

Internal CESSDA review report for SSHOC Deliverable 1.6: Data Management Plan - DMP (2021)

Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020:

https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf

“Turning FAIR into Reality”: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/turning_fair_into_reality_1.pdf

The FAIR Principles and guidelines: <https://www.force11.org/group/fairgroup/fairprinciples>

DOI: <https://www.doi.org/>

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/>

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“FAIR Forever? Long Term Data Preservation Roles and Responsibilities, Final Report”:
<https://zenodo.org/badge/DOI/10.5281/zenodo.4574234.svg>

5. List of Tables

[Table 1: Presentation of SSHOC data sets' and data usages' as actual and future SSH resources](#)

[Table 2: Set of guiding principles to make data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable](#)